

SECTION OF HUMANITARIAN AND PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

(1946-1965) IRRIGATION AND MELIORATION WORKS IN FERGANA VALLEY AND THE BEGINNING OF RESETTLEMENT OF POPULATION TO NEWLY MASTERED LANDS

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Abstract

After the Second World War, the issues of irrigation and melioration in the Fergana Valley, as well as the resettlement of the population to newly mastered lands were analyzed and studied.

Keywords: the cotton growing, irrigation, melioration, land development, migration, cotton, reservoir, collector, drain.

On the eve of the Second World War, the construction of a large Fergana Canal, the commissioning of such large collars as Sariksuv and the construction of the "Okhunbobayev" canal created the necessary economic opportunities for the further development of Agriculture in a complex way.

Despite the difficulties of the period of the Second World War, irrigation and mastering of new lands were carried out in the Fergana Valley. The work carried out in the Fergana Valley Water Farm during this period was mainly aimed at restoring gidroinshoes by means of traditional insects and increasing the quantity of crop areas with the main attention. As a result, in 1941-1945 in the Fergana Valley regions, a total of 96000 hectares of new lands were acquired[1]. But, in its place, it is also worth noting that the main works on the irrigation and assimilation of Central Fergana lands during the war were initiated in all regions of the Fergana Valley at the beginning of the year 1943.

During this period, the restored gidroinshoots were built from local materials in a simple, temporary, that is, semi-engineering type, due to the lack of building materials and specialists.

In the years of war, as in the whole republic, the Fergana Valley was formed due to the non-observance of agrotechnical rules in the water economy, improving the reclamation of irrigated lands, cleaning, repair of collectors, ditches and trenches, that is, for the non-introduction of crop rotation, the process of salinization and waterlogging of agricultural lands was accelerated[2].

The analysis of the position of the Fergana Valley regions in the agricultural sector of the Republic in the first years after the Second World War shows that one of the main factors determining the development of the economy of this region was the rapid increase in cotton production in the first place. According to the plan laid down by the Soviet government, in 1946 in the Namangan region 78 thousand hectares, in the Fergana region 108 thousand hectares, and in the Andijan region 112 thousand hectares of land were assigned the task of growing cotton. In these regions, the yield from each hectare was supposed to be the highest figure in the Republic along with the Tashkent region, namely 16.0 hectares, 16.6 hectares and 17.6 hectares.

The tasks of such a plan were then given a stable trend, with the task of not only increasing cotton yield, but also expanding cotton crop areas. For example, according to the plan for the next 1947 year, the following tasks were set before the Fergana Valley regions:

In 1947, the USSR was determined to increase cotton cultivation by 100 000 hectares compared to the previous year, but a little later the Central Committee of the CP (b) of Uzbekistan put forward a plan for cotton yield in the March plenum (1947) of the regions due to the "minimum state duties", on the initiative of the party and Soviet organizations, collective farms and Sovkhoz of the Fergana Valley regions, it was determined to increase productivity to the Andijan region by 23.5 percent, to the Fergana region by 18 percent and to the Namangan region by 20 percent. In general, in this year, the Fergana Valley regions had to increase cotton production to 700 thousand tons[4].

The central Fergana massif of the Fergana Valley, as well as the Valley regions themselves, also has not yet mastered Reserve and burrow lands, which, of course, was a huge economic potential that was not used. Therefore, in 1947, it was planned to master 260,7 thousand hectares of land on the territory of the Uzbek SSR. As for the regions of the Republic, this task was reflected in the following figures: in Surkhondary-10,4 thousand, in Namanga-15,3 thousand, in Fergana-20,3 thousand, in Kashkady-21 thousand, in Samarkand-21,7 thousand, in Bukhara-23,2 thousand, in Khorezm-30 thousand, in Andijan-33 thousand, In Karakalpakstan-38.9 thousand hectares, while in the Tashkent region 46.9 thousand hectares were defined the task of mastering new lands[5].

The development of New Lands was initiated by the end of the Second World War in the regions of the Fergana Valley, including the Uzbek SSR, and the rapid implementation of this process was given great attention to the plenum of the above-mentioned Uzbek Communist Party.

At this conference, it was recognized that there are many shortcomings in the work carried out on the new reserve and burrow lands in this issue. Among these shortcomings, there was also the problem of mastering abandoned (perelogs) lands. It was necessary for collec-

tive farmers and mobilized brigades who were transferred to these Reserve and burrow lands at work and in household life there were no conditions. They are provided with housing, farm buildings, necessary agricultural weapons and working animals, and cultural and household conditions have not been created, as well as road construction has been carried out in a dead-lake manner.

The benefits and material resources given to the state-run farms were not used productively. As a result, as a result of these inadequacies allowed, the necessary result in the assimilation of new irrigated lands was not achieved, also, the portable Brigades, which should serve as the basis for the organization of new collective farms, were quickly destroyed because many people quit their jobs.

Since such shortcomings in the process of development of reserve and burrow lands were especially numerous in Andijan and Namangan regions, the leadership of these regions was subjected to severe criticism by the political leadership of the Republic and demanded from them to eliminate the existing shortcomings quickly[6].

The implementation of irrigation and melioration work would be a strong impetus not only to the situation in water-scarce areas, but also to increase yields on newly mastered lands. This plenum acknowledges the importance of addressing these issues at the same time, emphasizing that any attempts to counteract the productive use of irrigation facilities built before the construction of the new irrigation are extremely harmful.

Therefore, the leadership of the Republic recommends to the regions to proceed from the conditions of the districts in solving the problem of water scarcity. For example, as a result of the correct and productive use of water by the districts, where water supply is good and irrigation system is developed, the possibility of mastering new lands is created. And for the districts where the irrigation system was not well developed and water scarcity, the main task was to create conditions for the organization of large-scale construction of these new irrigation facilities, eliminating water scarcity and thereby expanding the appropriation of new irrigated lands [7].

Therefore, the construction of new irrigation facilities on a large scale in the productive organization of the acquisition and resettlement of the population of new lands to these lands was defined as an important task. This process is necessary not without hindrance to the development of irrigation, but to facilitate further development of cotton wool.

To carry out such tasks, the following tasks were set before the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the leadership of the regions:

- According to the decision of the government of the USSR on February 2, 1946, to ensure the premature implementation of the construction of a new irrigation system in the Republic this year and on this basis to master 230 thousand hectares of irrigated land;

- In the year 1947, the capacity of Kattakurgan water was increased by 200 million cubic meters. and in 1948 year, as indicated in the capacity of his project

650 million cubic meters. completion of construction work on the delivery of meters;

- To complete the main works in the year 1947 in the water of the Middle East and complete its construction in the next year;

- In 1947, completion of construction works on the northern Tashkent, Jun, Dyushambinka-Karatogh, Tashkent channels, on the Sarikkurgan gidrotechnik Uzel, as well as starting work on the Channel "Okhumboboev[8]

Thus, the construction of such a large-scale new irrigation in the Republic by the Soviet government and the leadership of the Uzbek SSR in 1947-1948 years was necessary not only for the development of irrigation facilities, but also for the development of new irrigated lands. In carrying out these tasks, the transfer of the population to newly mastered lands, the organization of new rural collective farms and sovkhozs became one of the structural and important aspects of this policy.

Huge work has been carried out on the development of Central Fergana lands in the Fergana Valley. Since the 30 - ies of the XX century, several practical activities have been carried out in the field of irrigation, melioration and improvement of existing irrigation systems of new lands. During this period, a large Fergana, Northern and Southern Fergana, " Okunboboev " canal and other water facilities were built. A large drying system of yellow water covering 200 thousand hectares of land, Karakalpak and other collector drainage systems have been built. As a result of the construction of large-scale irrigation facilities, improvement in the use of Water Resources in Fergana, Andijan and Namangan regions, in particular, gave the opportunity to use the water of the sersuv Naryn River[9].

The tasks for the effective use of new lands and the further development of irrigation farming were also set out in the directives on the further development of the USSR national economy from 1951 to 1955. It is expected that the construction of such irrigation systems as Sirdarya, Zarafshan and Kashkadarya rivers basins, Central Fergana will continue in these regions[10].

The implementation of such work, that is, the irrigation system, in turn, gave the opportunity to master new lands and involve them in agricultural production. As a result, in Central Ferghana, an opportunity was created to use the fertile Reserve and burrow lands, which were laid empty in large quantities.

In order to make these lands more readily available, the collective farmers of Andijan, Namangan and Fergana regions appealed to the government "to carry out irrigation work on these lands on the account of Indivisible funds of collective farms". To this end, in 1953, the construction trust "Ferganvodstroy" was established, and in the regions-the construction installation offices, which carry out irrigation of new lands on the account of Indivisible funds of collective farms.

In its place, it is worth noting that, according to the decision of the government of the USSR, the provision of construction trust "Ferganvodstroy" with funds for the construction of residential and production buildings

on newly mastered lands, as well as landfill, excavators, auto-transport and other equipment was carried out on the account of the state budget. As a result, this organization was also fully provided with various funds and equipment.

The newly mastered lands of the Namangan region are located in the massifs of Damkul, Akkum, Momokhon, Achykul, Nayman and Boz, after mastering these lands in the second half of the 1950 years, more than 30 collective farms with an area of 1,5-1,6 thousand hectares each were established. In the newly mastered lands, cotton is planted on 30 thousand hectares of land[11].

In general, the further development of Agriculture in the Fergana Valley is similar, which can be observed on the example of the Andijan region. For example, in this region, the cotton crop area increased from 1955 to 1965 year to 31.7 thousand hectares, and by 1965 it amounted to 179.6 thousand hectares[12].

By the middle of the 1950s, Fergana Valley collective farms had overshadowed social funds of sufficient production and monetary resources. For example, in the kolkhozs in the Namangan region by 1 January 1956 there were 270 thousand sums of money, which were planned to be spent for further development of pakhtachilikni by expanding the water-scarce kolkhoz farm and mastering new lands[13].

In the decree of the Soviet of Ministers of the USSR and the CPSU MK "on further development of pakhtachilikni in 1954-1958 in UZSSR"[14] on February 9, 1954, 142 thousand hectares in the Fergana Valley, of which 116 thousand hectares in Central Fergana were provided for land development and irrigation. In particular, from 1950 to 1954, 2803 hectares of land were acquired in the Boz district, and in 1953-1958 2960 hectares of land were acquired[15].

From 1954 to 1960, the central Fergana occupied 23 100 hectares of land and from 1960 to 1965 more than 17400 hectares of new land[16]. The districts of Boz, Yazyovon and Zadarya (now Mingbulak), specializing in cotton growing, have been established on the lands that have been mastered.

It is worth noting that although the gross weight of cotton cultivation in the Republic increased year by year, in 1951-1955 the productivity did not rise, on the contrary, there were cases of decline. 21,1 ts from the earth you ga In 1950-1953 years each. in 1954, he made 20,1 Centner, in 1955 18,9 Centner, and in 1955, respectively. As a result, the gross yield also decreased: in 1955, less than 200 thousand tons of cotton was produced last year[17].

Cotton fields in Andijan region reached 164.7 thousand hectares in 1954 (in 1953 it was 150 thousand hectares). Cotton crop 1953 year 24 ts. ni if organized, then in 1954 year on average 28,5 ts per hectare. until harvest was received. In five years, 48 thousand hectares of new lands were introduced into agricultural consumption in the province, consisting of 32 thousand hectares of irrigated land and 16 thousand hectares of unused land in the irrigation system. Only in 1954 year 15.9 thousand hectares of new land were acquired in the region[18].

In 1956 year, the Republic had a total area of 2,7 million hectares of irrigated land. But, nevertheless, the Soviet government demanded a further increase in the number of irrigated crop areas on account of the appropriation of new lands.

According to the above-mentioned decision of the Soviet government, by 1964, Mirzachul himself was assigned the task of mastering 300 thousand hectares of land before the Uzbek SSR[19].

In order to implement this plan, major projects such as the construction of huge hydrotechnical structures – Central and Southern Mirzachul channels, as well as the expansion of the Northern Mirzachul channel named after Kirov-were to be implemented in the territory of the Republic in the next 5-6 years. It was also planned to build a Mirzachul hydroelectric power station with a capacity of 40 thousand kw, a railway with a length of 60 km from Sirdarya to Jizzakh. The implementation of such works as 23 cotton farms, 23 cotton cleaning plants, construction of roads, installation of means of communication was also indicated in this decision[20].

During the period from 1953 to July 1, 1957, the construction trust "Ferganvodstroy" carried out outstanding work in the field of water management construction with the aim of irrigation and drying of the Central Fergana Massif. From the account of the state budget, a large number of settlements, repair organizations, concrete plants, buses, garages, woodworking plants and other auxiliary organizations were built[21].

During this period, residential areas of 20 thousand square meters were completed and commissioned for use by builders. Work was started to improve the irrigation melioration of reserve and burrow lands in the area of 58 thousand ha. The survey of irrigation-melioration preparations of 44 thousand hectares of land was completed, capital planning was carried out on 14 thousand hectares of land[22].

In addition to the construction of Water Resources, other works, including the planning of land plots, the construction of highways, the construction of kolkhoz villages, the excavation of artesian wells, etc., have been carried out in the development of new lands.

But there were a number of shortcomings in the performance of these works. Until 1957, the organizations working in Central Fergana carried out their activities independently and there was no close contact and contact between them. Since there was no general scheme for irrigation and assimilation of the central Fergana (it was established only in 1957 year), the implementation of these works was not carried out according to one single plan, but also there was no organization coordinating the work of various enterprises. Only from 1957 year as a collective organization for the Coordination of water management construction, the Central Fergana Irrigation and mastering Soviet was established. As a result, the foundation was laid for a single organization that deals with all the issues of mastering new lands, production and construction of cultural and household buildings, roads[23].

In the second half of the 1950 years, the main construction of the channel named after Okhunboboev was completed by construction organizations, as a result of

which the channel's ability to conduct water increased significantly. At the same time, several large networks were built out of the channel, and their head structures were made of concrete and reinforced concrete. Also, large collars such as moths and scabies were built, while Damkul collars were built, several hundred kilometers of irrigation canals and drains were built[24]. As a result, an abandoned land area of 14271 hectares, including 13741 hectares of protected land and 540 hectares of land in the Ulugnor area, was prepared for irrigation. But at the same time there were shortcomings in the assimilation of new lands. Due to the fact that the channel "okhunboboev" was not installed at the time of construction in the Sovkhoz sector, water was not supplied to this channel in the required amount when the water in the Sirdarya decreased.

The scale of the work carried out in the Fergana regions in the assimilation of the central Fergana steppes was different. For example, according to the Namangan region in 1957 year the following work had to be done: On the system of the channel "Oxunboboev" received 15 million rubles. 882 thousand cubic meters of land works, 19.4 thousand cubic meters of concrete and reinforced concrete works, 2.7 million cubic meters of land works on the Western Yazyovon and Akkul massif and 3,0 thousand cubic meters of concrete and reinforced concrete works, 12 million tons of Ackul. It was planned to carry out 325 thousand cubic meters of Land Works and 12,3 thousand cubic meters of concrete and reinforced concrete works[25].

Until 1963 year in Central Fergana, 60 thousand hectares of protected land were appropriated. A huge Fergana channel played a huge role in raising yields on the lands that were expelled from the former. In the same year, productivity amounted to 24 cents per hectare[26]. Until 1964 year, in the newly irrigated areas of the Valley, more than 2000 km of various canals, more than 2000 km of underground canals-pipes and collars, more than 7000 hydrotechnical structures were built[27].

It is worth noting that in 1953-1963 in Central Fergana 72,54 thousand hectares of protected land were irrigated and prepared in terms of irrigation-melioration[28].

For example, in the Namangan region, such roads existed from Shahand bridge to Yazyovon, from Mingbulak to Karakalpak, from Karakalpak to Pungon, from Larch to Chust and from Mingbulak to Yazyovon, and it was necessary to link the new collective farms established in Central Fergana with other regions and ensure the development of socio-economic processes. But in carrying out these works, a lot of work was carried out in full, due to the fact that the Soviet leadership did not pay enough attention to the social sphere.

At the same time, in order to improve the economic activity of new farms and create its structure, it was planned to build 4 cotton-growing units, one cotton-cleaning plants in the Zadarya region (now a thousand-acre) and Karakalpakstan, as well as many other institutions[29].

It is worth noting that the policy of relocation was carried out not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the Union

as a whole, including in such allied republics as the RSFSR, the Georgian SSR, the Kazakh SSR, the Belarusian SSR, the Azerbaijani SSR[30]. The course of this policy was organized and strictly controlled by the Soviet leadership. Moving the population and the organization of new sovkhozs and collective farms is a responsible task, with the purpose of its implementation under the government of Uzbekistan "Department of relocation" was created. His task was entrusted to such tasks as the restoration of new collective farms and Soviets on the lands to be mastered, the organization of the resettlement of people from densely populated lands in order to provide them with labor force.

If we consider the dynamics of relocation of population to collective farms established on newly mastered lands in 1952-1953 at the crossroads of the USSR and the regions of Uzbekistan, this process was as follows: in the Tashkent region in 1952 instead of 4200 farms in the plan 4597 units (109.4%), in 1953 instead of 2100 families in the plan[31].

The policy of mastering new lands and resettlement to these lands, which began in the post-war years in the Republic, was carried out with the aim of increasing cotton cultivation in the first place. This process was later brought to a stable tone, and in the following years it was also considered by the Soviet and republican governments as one of the main factors in the development of Agriculture. This factor can be seen on the example of the adoption of the resolution of the Soviet of Ministers of the USSR on February 11, 1954 "Uzbekistan on further development of pakhtachilikni in the USSR 1954-1958". According to this decision, only in 1954 year it was planned to transfer 600 thousand farms to collective farms in the newly mastered irrigation lands[32].

In general, in 1954-1958, 40 thousand farms were to be transferred to newly mastered lands in the USSR mainly from non-irrigated regions of the Republic. In the cross-section of the years, this was reflected as follows: in 1955, 7000 units, in 1956, 8000 units, in 1957, 9,000 units, and in 1958, 10 000 units were moved, and the number of farms to be moved every year should have increased by 1000[33].

This, in turn, would create an opportunity for the economic growth of the Republic, including the development of the construction sector. For example, only in 1954 year for the displaced population was planned to build about 6500 housing units in the Uzbek SSR.

It is worth noting that in the second half of the 1950s, the resettlement of the population to newly mastered lands increased to the level of state policy, and this process began massively not only in the USSR, but also in other Soviet republics. This socio-economic process has remained one of the inseparable parts of Soviet Agrarian Policy for many years.

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